

MODEL OF FACTORS AFFECTING NIGHT-TIME ECONOMY DEVELOPMENT IN VIETNAM

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Abstract

The night-time economy is an integral part of the larger economic landscape. Developing this sector aims to boost domestic consumption, particularly in the tourism industry, and contribute to the overall economic growth of the country. This study seeks to establish a theoretical framework and build a model to identify and analyze the factors influencing the development of Vietnam's night-time economy. Employing a qualitative research approach, the authors leverage existing literature on the subject to establish a theoretical foundation for their model. Their findings reveal five key factors, both direct and indirect, that impact the development of Vietnam's night-time economy: (1) tour organization, (2) tourism route planning, (3) diverse tourism products, (4) local cultural development, and (5) engaging events and activities. These factors operate through two mediating variables: "Destination" (full mediator) and "Management of exploiting resources" (partial mediator).

Keywords: Model, Influencing Factor, Night Economic, Vietnam.

1. INTRODUCTION

Develop the night-time economy to promote consumption behavior and develop tourism, focusing on developing 04 areas: i) Cultural, entertainment, and recreation services; ii) Catering services; iii) Shopping services; iv) Tourism in areas with potential to develop the night-time economy. More and more businesses and service providers are expanding their operating hours in the evening, night-time economy activities to attract more social classes and become more and more inclusive through serving many different

demographic groups. In fact, in Vietnam, popular types of night-time economies have been deployed in some large cities with developed tourism industries such as Hanoi, Ho Chi Minh City, Da Nang, Hoi An, Da Lat... shown in the model of night markets, night streets, bars, tea rooms, 24/24 convenience store chains, walking streets or routes. Typical entertainment streets, such as: Ta Hien (Hanoi), Bui Vien (Ho Chi Minh City), Ba Na Hills (Da Nang)... Since starting to implement the plan to open walking streets and night markets in 2019, from 2016 to now, Hanoi has organized more than 300 large-scale cultural events, attracting the participation of 8 provinces and cities nationwide and 17 countries around the world. Although there are many advantages for developing the night-time economy such as a stable and safe political system and an increasingly improved human security index, the night-time economy in Vietnam is still developing slowly and has not yet developed a unique brand that attracts domestic and foreign tourists. Especially international visitors feel unattracted because coming to Vietnam there are not many options for fun and relaxation at night. Night-time economy activities have only been exploited on a small scale, individually in some areas, and have not yet made a mark (Pham, 2023).

New points in the model are:

- Build a model of factors directly and indirectly affecting night-time economy development in Vietnam. The research focuses on the dependent variable which is Night-time economy development in Vietnam. Next, the authors built two intermediate variables: Destination and Resource Exploitation Management. These variables were formed with the focus on bridging the factors that affect the development of the night-time economy in Vietnam, thereby creating the perfection of the research model.
- Propose some implications for tourism industry managers and night tourism development, as well as help them understand the factors affecting night tourism development in Vietnam.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Concept of night-time economy

The night-time economy is a concept that represents the focus on developing service activities that take place from 6:00 p.m. the previous night to 6:00 a.m. the next morning, such as cultural, entertainment, sports, entertainment, and service services. dining, shopping, travel, festivals, family events. The night economy is divided into "Evening Economy" (from 06:00 the previous night to 0:00 a.m. the next morning) and "Late Night Economy" (from 0:00 a.m. to 06:00 a.m.).

The concept of the night-time economy first appeared in the 1970s in the United Kingdom and Europe. When Europe's industrial cities began to experience crisis after transforming from production centers to consumption centers. The phrase "Night Economy" is considered equivalent to the concept of "24-hour City". Initially, the term had a negative connotation, as it was closely associated with increased violence and greater damage to the city center as bars stayed open longer than before and sold alcohol in larger quantities

at low prices, as noted in the studies of Hobbs et al. (2003). The night economy, in a broad sense, includes all social, cultural and productive activities that take place during the night time frame. In Australia, the night-time economy includes business activities that serve human consumption needs at night. In a narrow sense, the night-time economy is a combination of economic and cultural activities that take place at night, mainly entertainment experiences (excluding the prostitution industry). In the US, the night-time economy includes 5 main areas including: Arts, bars, culinary services, sports and entertainment. Most European countries define the night-time economy in a narrow sense and define the night-time economic operating time frame from 6:00 p.m. the previous day to 6:00 a.m. the next morning (Field 2008; Le et al., 2022).

The concept of Night Economy is service activities that take place after 6:00 pm the previous night until 6:00 am the next morning, including: Shopping at night markets, 24/24 convenience stores; cuisine, art, music; entertainment programs, festivals, events, and tourist attractions are only open at night. The night-time economy is increasingly being exploited by many countries and is considered a new economic growth activity. The night-time economy is attracting the attention of many countries, especially countries with developed tourism industries, including Vietnam. The project for developing the night economy in Vietnam was issued by the Prime Minister along with Decision No. 1129/QĐ-TTg dated July 27, 2020 with the goal of exploiting the potential for developing the night economy. This is considered a step that marks the opening of opportunities for strong development of the night economy in urban areas with seaports and domestic tourist cities with the goal of exploiting the potential for developing the night economy and making the most of multiple opportunities for economic development, improving income and people's lives. Recently, the Ministry of Culture, Sports and Tourism also approved a project on several models for developing night tourism products. The project targets in the next three years some major tourist centers such as Hanoi, Quang Ninh, Thua Thien Hue, Da Nang, Khanh Hoa, and Ho Chi Minh City, Can Tho... have at least one model for developing night tourism products (Thuy Bich, 2023).

2.2. Related studies on night-time economy development

2.2.1. Tours affect the development of the night-time economy

A tour is defined as a travel itinerary planned and organized by a travel company, including services such as transportation, accommodation, meals, sightseeing, etc. Martins et al. (2017) focused on studying the impact of night tourism on the local economy in Lisbon, a European city with high tourism growth. The study focuses on exploiting night tourism factors that can create many economic benefits for the locality, including creating new jobs, increasing income and enhancing public infrastructure. In particular, night tourism can create new business opportunities and promote the development of related industries such as restaurants, bars and other entertainment activities. Jeroen et al (2020) used data from 28 European countries, 10 Dutch cities and 8 tourism businesses in Rotterdam to evaluate the relationship between tourism and the night-time economy. The results show that tourism has a positive impact on the night-time economy at all three levels, but the degree of impact varies depending on the type of tourism and night-time

economy. Specifically, domestic tourism has a greater impact than international tourism at the national level; Cultural tourism has a stronger influence than recreational tourism at the city level; and tourism businesses are said to be more adaptable to the night-time economy. Rui and colleagues (2022) argue that the night-time tourism economy is a continuing part of the day-time economic activity, meeting the growing material and cultural consumption needs of local residents and tourists in experiencing local culture and local lifestyle. This study evaluates the overall sustainable development trend of the night-time tourism economy and explores the development path of the night-time tourism economy through a cluster analysis of the night-time tourism economy in Barcelona (excerpted from Nguyen et al., 2023). Nguyen (2023) commented that tours help tourists access night-time economy activities conveniently and save time. In addition, tours are also an effective form of promoting night-time economy activities. Night-time economy activities and tour organization activities create many jobs and increase income for local people. The author also has suggestions to further promote the role of tour organizations in developing the night-time economy such as: should synchronously invest and modernize infrastructure and technical facilities to serve the needs night-time economy service to meet the needs of tourists; There needs to be close coordination between state agencies, businesses and localities to develop the night-time economy in a sustainable way; There needs to be programs to promote, introduce, and promote night tourism to attract more tourists to visit and experience.

2.2.3. Destinations affect night-time economy development

Tourism destination is a popular concept and has many angles to analyze in the field of tourism, referring to the place where tourism activities take place and also where tourism management and its impacts occur when that location is made. Destination refers to a place that attracts tourists because of the diversity of resources, quality and range of amenities and other services provided to visitors. The destination can be a continent, a country, an island or a town, a place where tourists come to visit, or a place with a separate political regime and legal framework that is applied. Applying different marketing plans as well as provide tourism products and services to customers, especially where the place must be given a specific brand name (Davidson and Maitland, 2000; Batat, 2021). Farina and Arslan (2016) argue that a destination is also considered a geographical area defined by tourists, where there are technical facilities and services to meet the needs of tourists (quoted from Nguyen et al., 2023). Charoenwong and colleagues (2018) conducted a study of 300 night tourism businesses in Bangkok, Thailand. The results show that nightlife destinations have a positive impact on local tourism by attracting tourists and prolonging their stay. Specifically, visitors to nightlife destinations tend to stay longer and spend more than visitors to destinations without nightlife activities. Maria and colleagues (2022) also used data from 150 night-time tourism businesses in Barcelona, Spain to conclude that night-time destinations play an important role in local economic development through creating jobs, increasing income and promoting revenue growth. Specifically, night-time destinations generate 15% of jobs, 20% of income and 25% of revenue for night-time tourism businesses in Barcelona and show that night-time destinations play an important role in local economic development

through creating jobs, increasing income and promoting growth for the night tourism industry (excerpted from Huertas et al., 2022).

The above studies all show that destinations have a positive impact on night-time economy development. Specifically, the destination attracts tourists to visit and experience nightlife activities, thereby promoting tourist spending and creating more job opportunities and economic growth for the locality.

2.2.4. Tourism products affect the development of the night-time economy

Tourism products are considered a combination of material and spiritual values of a country, a locality, or a facility that tourists come to enjoy and pay for (Xuan Huan, 2021). Research results by Nattapong and colleagues (2018) show that the night-time economy in Bangkok, Thailand is developing strongly with activities including: Entertainment activities such as night markets, restaurants, bars, discos, cinemas, cultural activities such as festivals, art performances and shopping activities at shopping centers, souvenir shops,... The night-time economy is a factor that attracts tourists, but also causes some security, traffic and environmental problems. Yingying and colleagues (2020) showed that the factors that attract tourists to night tourism activities in Shanghai, China include: the use of artistic lighting has contributed to creating special highlights. colors for night tourist destinations have attracted the attention of tourists; The organization of music events, art events, and street festivals has contributed to creating a vibrant and bustling atmosphere for night tourist areas; The use of modern art and technology has contributed to creating unique and exciting experiences for visitors. Tran (2021) has proven that the tourism service factor has an important influence on the night-time economy and is of significant importance. Therefore, developing night tourism service activities in a country like Vietnam can create many economic opportunities and bring clear benefits to the local economy. Night-time tourism services generate income for the state budget and benefit businesses, creating job opportunities and attracting tourists. Nguyen and colleagues (2022) also believe that night tourism can create new tourism products such as night tours, night entertainment activities and special events that only take place at night. . This helps diversify tourism products and increase the attractiveness of tourist destinations. With more night-time economy services and activities, tourists can spend more during their travel time. This can create new sources of income for businesses and increase tourism's contribution to the local economy.

The above studies all show that tourism products have a positive impact on the development of the night-time economy. Specifically, tourism products attract tourists to visit and experience nightlife activities, thereby motivating tourists to spend more and creating more job opportunities and economic growth for the locality. Therefore, improving the quality of tourism products is one of the important tasks of businesses and tourism agencies.

2.2.5. Managing and exploiting tourism resources affects the development of the night-time economy

According to the Vietnam Tourism Law (2017), managing and exploiting tourism resources is the process of using tourism resources reasonably and effectively, to meet the needs of tourists and bring economic benefits for local communities.

Marcia and Rivanda (2009) analyzed two public institutions in Curitiba and Foz do Iguaçu, Brazil to determine how organizational and tourism resources are used in public planning and management in the two cities. The results show that the main resource for public policy implementation is organizational architecture. However, the most important resource in public tourism management is the existence of tourism resources and organizational resources related to internal and external relationships, as well as organizational culture. position. Nguyen (2020) analyzed the advantages, difficulties, opportunities and challenges in attracting annual tourists, and proposed a number of measures to help develop the night-time economy in the new period in Thanh Hoa. Ho Chi Minh City is to properly exploit tourism resources, such as organizing entertainment programs, festivals, and special events at night, which also plays an important role in developing the night-time economy. This can attract tourists and local people to participate in fun activities, cultural exchanges, enjoy cuisine, shopping and create a source of income for urban residents. Pham (2021) believes that properly managing and exploiting tourism resources can create new sources of income for night-time economy activities, such as hotels, restaurants, bars and entertainment services. another mind. Increased promotion and marketing will create interest and attract tourists to night-time economy activities and services as well as improved infrastructure and services that will facilitate these night-time economy activities and attract tourists. In addition, ensuring security, safety and convenience in traveling and sightseeing at night for tourists is something that localities need to pay top attention to. Nguyen (2022) shows that the impact of managing and exploiting tourism resources can affect night-time economic development through night-time tourism activities such as cultural tourism and culinary tourism, dining, leisure travel, and other shopping and entertainment activities. Night-time tourism activities can generate income for local businesses and residents, increase business activity and create employment opportunities. In addition, night-time tourism can also enhance the development of related economic sectors such as restaurants, hotels, transportation, and other tourism services.

In summary, managing and exploiting tourism resources is of great importance to the night-time economy in cities. Investing in infrastructure, planning and management, exploiting and using tourism resources appropriately along with creating unique entertainment activities and events at night will contribute positively to the development of the night-time economy and create benefits for both tourists and local people.

2.2.6. Indigenous cultural development affects the development of the night-time economy

Developing indigenous culture is taking advantage of and developing the unique cultural values of a locality, to create unique tourism experiences and attract tourists. Developing indigenous culture not only helps preserve and promote the cultural characteristics of an area, but also contributes to the economic and social development of the local community.

Row and Holland (2011) initially focused their research on the concept of "night-time economy" which has become important in the urban policies of many cities around the world. Through this, a more complex approach to night culture is proposed, in order to better understand the lived experience of night culture. By considering night-time culture as a system of contexts in which environment, culture, governance regimes and markets interact. The study also emphasizes the important role of understanding indigenous cultural elements in the development of the night-time economy and proposes a new approach to understanding night-time culture within modern urban areas. Dang (2013) focuses on researching 4 issues: content, characteristics, nature and trends of globalization; cultural globalization; the role of culture in the world economy; the role of culture in tourism business in Vietnam, thereby pointing out the trend of exploiting cultural values in tourism business in Vietnam to create unique products, imbued with national identity. The development of various types of cultural tourism, as well as the establishment of cultural standards in tourism business and management, need to be carried out in close relationship with the overall development of the entire industry as well as the road ahead. the country's socio-economic development. At the same time, based on analyzing the relationship between cultural acculturation and international tourism development, Le and Nguyen (2013) analyzed and clarified young people's perceptions and reactions to these factors. culture of foreign tourists; recognizes young people's assessment of traditional cultural changes, especially changes in their own behavior in the context of current international tourism development. Tran (2021) emphasizes the important role of indigenous cultural development in promoting the night-time economy, which can create many opportunities to exploit tourism potential and attract tourists. At the same time, creating night-time entertainment and shopping activities can also attract investors and enhance local economic resources. Therefore, developing indigenous culture plays an important role in creating a favorable environment for the night-time economy. In the current context, cultural change is a research issue that receives attention. The above studies show that indigenous cultural development can contribute to the development of the night-time economy through the creation of attractive, indigenous tourism products and activities, contributing to promoting participation. participation, image of local communities and increased awareness of indigenous culture.

2.2.7. Events and activities affect the development of the night-time economy

Events and night-time economy activities not only bring cultural benefits but also play an important role in preserving and developing many aspects of local social and economic life. According to Tung (2021), these events and activities not only create unique cultural experiences but also promote the interference between local culture and international

culture, helping to build a diverse living environment. diverse and rich, while preserving local cultural identity. Zhao and Zhang (2021) believe that events and night-time economy activities also contribute to building a sustainable future, creating employment opportunities, helping reduce poverty and improving the quality of life for the community. local. At the same time, these activities help encourage the use of clean energy, reduce environmental pollution, and protect the environment, thereby contributing to sustainable development. Yigitcanlar et al. (2021) emphasized that night-time economy events and activities not only help stimulate economic growth in the region but also create new business opportunities, attract tourists, and enhance economic growth. strengthen the local position in the international economy. Overall, they are not only a part of culture but also a powerful driving force for global economic development. Adetoro and Idowu (2022) are concerned that events and night-time economy activities play an important role in improving the quality of life. By creating leisure and relaxation activities after work, they not only promote social interaction and connection but also create a vibrant, attractive living environment. This not only attracts people to live and work but also contributes to building a community with a high quality of life. Finally, Al-Saifi and Hassan (2022) argue that night-time economy events and activities can be seen as an important element in urban management to enhance security, order and social safety, minimizing environmental pollution and noise, thereby creating a green, clean, and beautiful living environment. This improves quality of life but also enhances urban management efficiency, creating an attractive and sustainable city.

3. RESEARCH METHODS

The first phase of this research involved a qualitative research methodology approach, conducted through focus group discussions. These discussions are a way to help elicit diverse perspectives, helping with the preliminary experiment and interview process and screening of factors affecting the development of the night-time economy in Vietnam. Based on the insights of experts and existing documents on night-time economy development, the fundamental factors have been identified and they have been adjusted to suit reality. From there, a model of factors affecting the development of the night-time economy in Vietnam was formed. After the preliminary qualitative phase, the research continued with the modification and expansion of observed variables, serving the later quantitative research phase.

4. RESEARCH MODEL AND HYPOTHESES

4.1. Research models

Through studying the theoretical basis and related research works of domestic and foreign authors in section 2.2., there are 37 related studies referenced by the authors to build a theoretical framework and propose a conceptual framework on the influence of 07 factors on the development of the night-time economy in Vietnam. A conceptual framework based on the 37 main theoretical studies above was inherited and developed by the authors to build a model of factors affecting the development of the night-time

economy in Vietnam. Factors such as Tour Organization, Route, Tourism Products, Indigenous Cultural Development, Events and Activities, Destinations and Management, Exploitation of Resources that Affect Night-time economy Development in Vietnam through two intermediary factors: Destination and Resource Exploitation Management. In which the factor of Management and exploitation of resources directly impacts the factor of Destination and Development of the night-time economy in Vietnam. Thereby, the authors proposed a research model as illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Proposed research model "Factors affecting the development of the night-time economy in Vietnam"

4.2. Research hypothesis

- Hypothesis H1: Tour organization has a positive (+) influence on Destination
- Hypothesis H2: Route has a positive (+) influence on Destination.
- Hypothesis H3: Tourism products have a positive (+) influence on Destination.
- Hypothesis H4: Indigenous cultural development has a positive (+) influence on Destination.
- Hypothesis H5: Events and activities have a positive (+) influence on Destination.
- Hypothesis H6: Destination has a positive (+) influence on night-time economy development in Vietnam.
- Hypothesis H7: Management and exploitation of resources have a positive (+) influence on Destination.
- Hypothesis H8: Management and exploitation of natural resources have a positive (+) influence on night-time economy development in Vietnam.

5. PROPOSED RESEARCH DIRECTIONS

This literature review can be useful in providing more comprehensive policies, business strategies and solutions to tourism industry managers and night tourism developers, as well as helping them understand Factors affecting the development of night tourism in Vietnam.

- a) In addition to the 7 factors that directly and indirectly affect the development of the night-time economy in Vietnam mentioned above, there are other factors that need to be researched to learn more about the impact of these factors on the development of the night-time economy in Vietnam.
- b) The conceptual framework in this study can be applied to other provinces and cities in Vietnam.
- c) This conceptual framework can be used by a number of State units in general and the Tourism industry in particular, as well as tourism companies in Vietnam to plan business policies.

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